

Electronic Supplementary File "Marker values"

Title: A mechanistic account of visual discomfort

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Figure 1. Metric values for all the stimuli in set Architecture 1. The second (respectively, third, fourth) column shows the values of activation (E) of the model response (respectively, sparseness -S-, isotropy -H- of the model response) against the average rating of discomfort for the whole set (grey dots) and the value for the image on the left (orange dot). Numbers at the top of each plot show the ranking of the image metrics with respect to the whole set.

Figure 1. Continues from previous page.

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